

Study of Dielectric Properties and Dipole Moments of Mn(II) Salts of Some Fatty Acids in Benzene Solutions

(MISS) LEEBA G. PARDESHI

Department of Chemistry, Government College of Arts and Science, Aurangabad-431 001

Manuscript received 4 September 1980, revised 11 May 1981, accepted 5 November 1981

The dipole moments of Mn(II) salts of palmitic, stearic and oleic acids were calculated by the methods of Gopalkrishna, Smyth-Dasgupta, Halverstadt-Kumler and Guggenheim. The values were calculated by Cole-Cole plots and parameters ϵ_0 , ϵ_∞ and α were determined. From the plots of $\log \tau$ vs $1/T$, ΔH , ΔF and ΔS were evaluated. In the present investigation, dipole moment values obtained by Gopalkrishna method compared favourably with those obtained by Guggenheim method.

THE present author has reported several studies on dipole moments and dielectric and other properties of salts of fatty acids. These include dipole moments and relaxation studies on Cu(II) stearate¹, Cu(II) oleate², pyridine adducts of salts of fatty acids³, effect of the salts of fatty acids on $KMnO_4$ ⁴⁻⁶ and others^{7,8}.

The present paper envisages to cover the dipole moments and dielectric relaxation properties of Mn(II) in all its aspects employing all possible recognised methods in literature. The initial problem faced by a worker in such studies is the sorting out of dielectric loss due to direct current conduction and one due to absorption. The present author being naturally interested in the latter conducted studies to ascertain whether the loss was due to absorption alone. This will be clear from Table 1 which gives the data involved in the well known expression :

$$\sigma = 5.5 \times 10^{-18} f \epsilon'' \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$$

where σ = specific conductance
 f = frequency in Hertz
 ϵ'' = the dielectric loss observed.

Since $\log \epsilon''/\log f$ ratios in the present investigation (Table 1) are far from unity, it was concluded that the losses observed here are due to absorption alone.

Temp. °C	$f \times 10^{-3}$	ϵ''	$\log f$	$\log \epsilon'' (-ve)$
System : Manganese palmitate-benzene				
34	260.0	0.2163	5.4150	0.6649
	272.5	0.0893	5.4354	1.0493
70	260.0	0.2082	5.4150	0.6815
	267.5	0.1160	5.4273	0.9851
System : Manganese stearate-benzene				
34	265.0	0.0984	5.4232	1.0068
	272.5	0.1147	5.4354	0.9408
70	260.0	0.2308	5.4150	0.6360
	275.0	0.0436	5.4393	1.3602
System : Manganese oleate-benzene				
34	257.5	0.2040	5.4108	0.6904
	265.0	0.1061	5.4232	0.8743
70	260.0	0.1272	5.4150	0.8955
	270.0	0.0762	5.4314	1.1181

Experimental

The salts were prepared by double decomposition method from the sodium salts of the fatty acids and the chloride of the metal, the latter added in slight excess. However, the purest salts were prepared by the method described earlier². The elemental analysis of the salts is in good agreement with the calculated values.

The dielectric constant, ϵ' , and dielectric loss, ϵ'' were measured on DK-06 WTW decimeter as described earlier¹. The values of ϵ_0 and ϵ_∞ were obtained from the Cole-Cole plots of dielectric constant ϵ' vs dielectric loss ϵ'' on X axis⁹. The values of relaxation time were calculated using the expression

$$\frac{u}{v} = \omega \tau (1 - \alpha)$$

where v = distance on the Cole-Cole plot between ϵ_0 and experimental point,

u = distance on the Cole-Cole plot between ϵ_∞ and experimental point.

ω = angular frequency.

The enthalpy, ΔH , entropy, ΔS , and molar energies, ΔF , were calculated from the plots of $\ln \tau$ vs $1/T$ using Eyring's equation. All the relevant data involved in these methods are set out in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES AND THE RELAXATION DATA AT TEMPERATURES 34, 50, 60 AND 70° FOR Mn(II) PALMITATE, STEARATE AND OLEATE IN THAT SERIAL ORDER. (ΔH , ΔF AND ΔS IN Kcal/mole)

Temp. °C	ϵ_0	ϵ_∞	α	τ	
34	2.2696	2.2589	0.08	2.13	$\Delta H = 2.50$
50	2.2391	2.2385	0.08	2.32	$\Delta F = 9.99$
60	2.2205	2.2125	0.27	3.05	$\Delta S = -0.044$
70	2.2140	2.2044	0.13	3.42	
34	2.2590	2.2513	0.40	2.88	$\Delta H = 3.54$
50	2.2314	2.2314	0.14	1.97	$\Delta F = 9.88$
60	2.2225	2.2135	0.24	2.19	$\Delta S = -0.0185$
70	2.2078	2.1967	0.05	1.23	
34	2.2345	2.2239	0.13	2.57	$\Delta H = 3.51$
50	2.2035	2.1928	0.18	2.05	$\Delta F = 9.78$
60	2.1864	2.1778	0.27	2.06	$\Delta S = -0.02$
70	2.1646	2.1564	0.32	1.80	

Thermodynamic quantities, ΔH , ΔF , and ΔS , are given in the last column of Table 2.

TABLE 3—DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES [$\mu(D)$] OF Mn(II) SALTS OF PALMITIC, STEARIC AND OLEIC ACIDS BY SMYTH-DASGUPTA'S (1), GOPALKRISHNA'S (2), HALVERSTADT-KUMLER'S (3) AND GUGGENHEIM (4) METHODS AT 34, 50, 60 AND 70°

Compound	Temp. °C	$\mu(D)$			
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
MnPT ₂	34	3.62	3.50	3.48	3.50
	50	3.85	4.16	1.45	4.08
	60	3.12	3.16	1.54	3.29
	70	3.63	4.19	2.35	3.92
MnST ₂	34	6.57	6.34	—	5.53
	50	7.32	4.90	—	5.96
	60	7.74	5.57	6.29	6.23
	70	8.67	6.04	10.18	6.63
MnOL ₂	34	1.97	—	—	5.65
	50	2.26	—	—	5.81
	60	2.66	—	—	5.72
	70	3.39	—	—	5.12

Results and Discussion

The methods of Gopalkrishna¹⁰, Smyth-Dasgupta¹¹, Halverstadt-Kumler¹² and Guggenheim¹³ were used to evaluate dipole moments of the salt at 34, 50, 60 and 70°. The Cole-Cole plots of dielectric constant ϵ' vs dielectric loss ϵ'' gave the values of ϵ_0 and ϵ_∞ on the X axis, which were used for calculating the μ values by the methods of Gopalkrishna and Smyth-Dasgupta.

Literature indicates that there is a great scope in determining the μ values of these salts, since a few salts like magnesium palmitate and calcium oleate¹⁴ and magnesium oleate^{15,16} have been studied and the dipole moment values reported are quite divergent. Palit *et al*¹⁷ have used the Guggenheim equation for the determination of μ values of metal salts of fatty acids.

Guggenheim equation was modified by Palit and Banerjee¹⁸ for a rational approach to the problem of computation of polarization and is given as :

$$P_s \mu = \frac{3M_s}{d(\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)} 2 \left[\left(\frac{\delta}{\delta W_s} (\epsilon - n^2) \right) \right]_0$$

The attractive feature of the Guggenheim method could be retained without sacrificing the accuracy perceptibly.

Since the dipole moment values showed a slightly erratic trend, a search was made to ascertain whether the solutions were colloidal. No such behaviour was noticed when a cone of light was passed through the 10⁻⁴ M solutions with the help of an arc appliance supplied with VNI SPECK constant deviation spectrometer.

In the present studies, the dipole moments are obtained by recent methods, namely those of Gopalkrishna and Smyth and Dasgupta. The μ values obtained by these two methods have consistently agreed with each other and have also been in agreement with those obtained by the Guggenheim

method. In Gopalkrishna's method, two plots are constructed to evaluate μ values which are interdependent. The values are very susceptible to the values of $[(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)]$ which are obtained from Cole-Cole plots. Halverstadt-Kumler method suffers from the serious defect of measurement of densities of solutions.

Hence it was concluded that the changes in μ observed may be attributed to viscosity changes⁸ in the benzene solutions of the salts. A rough estimate would be that if the viscosity increases with temperature, the orientation of the molecules will hinder and there will be fall in dipole moment. In the case of MnPT₂ solutions the flow time was observed to decrease in the temperature interval of 60~70°. As against this, it was seen to increase in MnOL₂ (60°~70°) and decrease in MnST₂ (50°~60°). Another explanation lies in the mesomorphic changes observed in the acids themselves which is carried to their salts.

Sydow¹⁹ has investigated the mesomorphic forms in the fatty acids from their ir spectra in the range of 0-13 μ . Sindaire *et al*²⁰ have observed in their studies of ir spectra of saturated hydrocarbons and esters of fatty acids that at least the two forms differ with respect to crystal axis. Phase transition was reported in some of the salts of fatty acids by X-ray diffraction.

The dipole moment values of palmitic, stearic and oleic acids are extremely small²¹⁻²³ and do not indicate any relationship between the chain length and the μ values. However, in the present investigation, the chain length is found to play a major role in that generally the dipole moment order²⁴ is MnST₂ > MnPT₂ > MnOL₂. This observation has been made by others in similar salts of magnesium. It is probable that the negative charge on the oleate, palmitate and stearate anions is distributed over the whole of the anion, much the same way as an electron cloud in an orbital, and hence the centre of gravity of charge lies further from the positive charge on the cation as the length of the chain goes on increasing. This may account for the order of μ as MnST₂ > MnPT₂ > MnOL₂.

The distribution parameter, α , is found to be dependent on the length of the chain and double bonded structure and increases generally with temperature. The entropy values, ΔS , are negative indicating an orderly orientation of these Mn(II) salts. This means free molar energies of these salts are larger than their enthalpy values. Again, the low values of ΔS suggest that the molecules of the Mn(II) salts must be orienting themselves as a whole without segments or cations in them taking any prominent part.

Chitoku and Higasi²⁵ have stated that if the molecular shape is spherical or vary but a little from the spherical shape, the relaxation times are slightly dependent on the viscosity of the medium. They, however, observed that if the molecules are asymmetrical in shape its dipole rotation in the

medium automatically involves displacement of vast number of neighbouring molecules and as a result the relaxation times depend markedly on the viscosity of media. Some calculations on Mn(II) salts studied here, carried out according to O'Dweyer and Sack method²⁶, show that the values differ largely from unity (a condition for spherical molecules) which according to these workers is a sure indication of asymmetry in the molecule.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Dr. R. A. Bhoze for helpful suggestions.

References

1. LEE LA PARDESHI and R. A. BHOZE, *Monatsh.*, 1977, **108**, 1235.
2. LEE LA PARDESHI and R. A. BHOZE, *Nat. Sc. J.*, 1976, **15**, 16.
3. LEE LA PARDESHI, A. RASHEED and R. A. BHOZE, *Rev. Roum.*, 1978, **23**, 1291.
4. P. D. JADHAV, LEE LA PARDESHI, A. RASHEED and R. A. BHOZE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 650.
5. P. D. JADHAV, LEE LA PARDESHI and R. A. BHOZE, *Nat. Sc. J.*, 1978, **10**, 17.
6. LEE LA PARDESHI, P. D. JADHAV and R. A. BHOZE, *Rev. Roum.*, 1979, **21a**, 1060.
7. LEE LA PARDESHI, A. RASHEED, S. N. KHODASKAR and R. A. BHOZE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 621.
8. LEE LA PARDESHI, A. RASHEED and R. A. BHOZE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18A**, 520.
9. K. S. COLE and R. H. COLE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, **19**, 1484.
10. K. V. GOPALKRISHNA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 767.
11. C. P. SMYTH and S. DASGUPTA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 5532.
12. I. F. HALVERSTADT and W. D. KUMLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **64**, 2988.
13. E. A. GUGGENHEIM, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 767.
14. W. OSTWALD and R. RIEDEL, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, **69**, 185.
15. B. C. BANERJEE and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 385.
16. N. PILPRL, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 893.
17. S. BHATNAGER, B. C. BANERJEE and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 175.
18. B. C. BANERJEE and S. R. PALIT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3952.
19. E. V. SYDOW, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 119.
20. R. G. SINCLAIRE, A. F. MAKAY and R. N. JONES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 2570.
21. K. L. WOLF, *Physik Z.*, 1930, **31**, 227.
22. M. P. VOTAROVICH and N. N. STEPANANKO, *Acta Physico. Chem. URSS*, 1940, **13**, 47.
23. M. A. ROLLIER, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1947, **77**, 366.
24. W. OSTWALD and R. RIEDEL, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, **59**, 150.
25. K. CHITOKU and K. HIGASHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1963, **36**, 1064.
26. J. J. ODWEYER and R. A. SACK, *Aust. J. Sc. Res. Ser.*, 1952, **A5**, 647.